

Business Analytics: The current research agenda

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ABSTRACT

Business analytics is the analysis of data and is a blend of various disciplines like Mathematics; Statistics; Economics; Operational Research; Artificial intelligence, Decision making (Psychological and behavioural sciences); Engineering (Electrical, computer sciences; Information systems, etc. This review on Business analytics and the current research agenda provides a multi-disciplinary synopsis on Business analytics on an establishment's decision-making process and allocation of resources keeping in perspective the behavioural, tactical, and administrative issues. The overall running theme that emerged from this review is that Business analytics is an emerging science based on people, processes, and outcomes of technology and helps organisations improve their overall operational productivity.

KEYWORDS: Business analytics, Decision making; Data value.

1. INTRODUCTION

Business analytics is the analysis of data to make significant decisions in the industry. Business analytics uses data science as its key element to developing new acumens of the business performances based on statistical methods, predictive modelling, data mining, and artificial intelligence algorithms.

Business analytics evolves at the main intersection of various disciplines like Mathematics; Statistics; Economics; Operational Research; Artificial intelligence, Decision making (Psychological and behavioural sciences); Engineering (Electrical, computer sciences; Information systems, etc. (Mortenson *et al.*, 2015).

The Digital revolution has changed the paradigm of modern methods of conducting business as it connects organisations, individuals, and devices interacting and collaborating at different levels. The data collected by the gadgets help to see patterns in the vast amorphous data, enhancing independent decision-making compared to the traditional methods of conducting business (Loebbecke and Picot, 2015).

The main concern in Business analytics is transforming "Big Data" into meaningful, evidence-based research by the organisations to make quick decisions that can help create value in commerce, trade, and industry (Davenport and Harris, 2007). Therefore this review focuses on the research agenda of the role of Business analytics on an establishment's decision-making process and allocation of resources keeping in perspective the behavioural, tactical, and administrative issues.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review has explained the subject of Business analytics and the current research plan based on the following headings.

2.1 Business analytics and teamwork

Insights into data modelling techniques are not enough for a decision-making process. It needs collaboration between business managers and data scientists to make sense of the structured and unstructured data and create new cognisance (Sharma *et al.*, 2014).

To benefit the outcome of the product design, multi-functional teams of the organisation have to appreciate the strategic importance of new technologies. Therefore, teamwork among individuals is an effective research plan to study the impact of business analytics on the organisation.

It is also vital to convert this new cognisance into value for the business in the form of cost and profitability and the examples expense from UPS parcel delivery and the shortest routes to save fuel (Drivers) (Kohli, 2007); airline industry and data warehousing (Watson 2001); casino members and their gambling behaviour, etc. (Sharma *et al.*, 2014).

2.2 Business analytics and decision making

To improve the quality of decision-making, it is imperative to invest in social capital, i.e. combining knowledge and resources across structural borders as strategic actions will eventually give rise to successfully implemented decisions (Blyler and Coff, 2003).

Good decisions have two vital origins that include "quality" (Drucker, 1967) and their acceptance by the stakeholders for their implementation, and more research is needed into acceptance of those decisions, especially by cross-functional teams (Vroom and Yetton, 1973).

2.3 Business analytics and data value

The contextual value data helps organisations to increase their operational efficiency. Data is an essential internal asset while caring out mergers and acquisitions of firms. An example can explain this viewpoint: when Microsoft bought LinkedIn in 2016 one of the main assets was its hundred million active users in the form of data. They paid a value of 26.2 billion for this acquisition (Microsoft, 2016).

To elicit the value of data as a research schema, the three most essential features to study are the value of the business and organisation, management of data, and data value chain (Günther *et al.*, 2017). The source of data and its modest advantage to the customer base, transaction information, product information and internal and external data sources are the main features that help calculate the value derived from data (Melville *et al.*, 2004).

The value of the data also depends upon how the organisations manage the data in turn on their business value. The data can have sensitive or non-sensitive information; privacy of the individuals from where the data is derived; storage of data; data governance; data visualisation and data-related decision making etc. boost the value of the data and the organisation as a whole (Günther *et al.*, 2017 and Melville *et al.*, 2004).

The current research agenda to study the value of data is factors that influence data, i.e. its reusability; decay over time; whether it is purchased, proprietary, or freely available; quality of the data; clustering of data according to its value-based data clustering techniques; data governance, i.e. sharing of data with customers and business associates, etc. (Otto, 2011).

2.4 Business analytics and business models

Schneider and Speith (2013) have expanded on the importance of business models to research business analytics. Business models help answer questions like- 'how the organisation works and earns money; 'how to commercialise inventions, and to put a price on service to their customers for correlated revenue'. Chesbrough (2010). As expounded by Chesbrough (2010), the barriers to business models are: confusion and obstruction and can be overcome with experimentation, qualitative case study approaches, and leadership. The various research agendas to better understand the business model innovations are the effects of business models on market structure, individual firm results, the firms, heterogeneity between firms, and their usage of resources (Priem and Butler, 2001 Penrose, 1959).

2.5 Business analytics with augmented and virtual reality

Big data is characterised by its sheer volume, validity, and value and needs quick decision-making abilities to decode it and implement its results. This can be possible by data visualisation techniques (Olshannikova, 2015). Many data visualisation platforms like Tableau, Wrangler, SAS, Augmented Reality (AR), Virtual Reality (VR), etc. that performs visualisation specific to business needs. AR and VR have found many uses in the healthcare, education, defence, industry gaming fields,

etc. This kind of data taken in vast amounts from different angles can enhance the visualisation experience.

2.6 Business analytics and information systems (IS)

The IS research on the information value chain is all about converting data to information- to knowledge -the action decision and back to generating data (Abbasi *et al.*, 2016). Each part of this chain involves the process, people, and technology, and further research agenda can focus on design, economics, and behaviour of IS. Additional research questions can focus on the return on investments on Big Data technologies, quantifying the damaging effects of incomplete or inaccurate information, which affects the data quality with implications on the business outcomes, social media marketing and its efficacy, etc. (Abbasi *et al.*, 2016).

2.7 Business analytics and e-services

Loukis *et al.* (2012) has illustrated the value of data collected from e-services such as e-learning, e-banking, e-government services into useful business analytics to improve the development and quality of the e-services. The authors have come up with a three-layer value model for the e-services, using an online questionnaire – the first layer measures the efficiency facet and value of the e-services, and the other layers concern themselves with the resources to perform various tasks to achieve their objectives and proficiencies it provides to the user. The research plan for e-services is based on evaluation data generated from the customers and is analysed and used for future e-services research. This method of research helps with continuous monitoring and evaluation for better optimisation at a lower cost.

2.8 Business analytics and tourism

Textual data generated from tourism sites like Trip advisor have found greater leverage in the business analytics of the hospitality industry to enhance their economies both reputation and cash wise and (Yoo *et al.*, 2016). The research outline, in this case, is based on customer feedback to enhance the quality of services. In turn, it can help managers understand the customer's experience right from arrival, their stay in the hotel. The main aspects they commented on will help in strategic decision making using research in the form of data mining techniques, NLP, to highlight some manoeuvres of the hotel's attributes to improve the customer experience.

3. CONCLUSION

This review provides a précis on the issues that surround business analytics. We identified teamwork, decision making, data value, business models, augmented and virtual reality, e-services, tourism, and information systems as important topics for further research. The overall running theme that emerged from this review is that Business analytics is an emerging science based on people, processes, and outcomes of technology and helps organisations improve their overall operational productivity.

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